

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

RESEARCH ON INTEGRATING IDEOLOGICAL AND POLITICAL ELEMENTS INTO HIGHER ALGEBRA CLASSROOM TEACHING --- TAKING SYSTEM OF LINEAR EQUATIONS AS AN EXAMPLE

Zhang Yu.

JiNing Normal University, School of Mathematics and statistic,
Ulanqab, Inner Mongolia, P. R. China

Research Project: 2022 Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region Education Science Research "14th Five-Year Plan" Project (NGJGH2022083)

Jining Normal University Teaching Reform and Research Project (JGKT2024045)

Abstract

After the national ideological and political conference for universities, institutions gradually began developing curriculum-based ideological and political education, exploring how to integrate these elements into college mathematics classrooms to create a new educational model. This paper first analyzes the current state of ideological and political education in higher algebra classes, then takes the teaching of "linear equations" as an example to discuss effective integration paths and strategies, and finally summarizes reflections and improvements on the integration of ideological and political elements. The research further indicates that this integration not only enhances students' mathematical thinking skills but also strengthens their sense of social responsibility and values.

Keywords: Ideological and Political elements; Higher algebra; Linear equations; Classroom teaching.

1 Introduction

In May 2014, during a discussion with teachers and students at Peking University, Xi Jinping stated, "Knowledge is an important foundation for establishing core values."^[1] Point out that knowledge is the foundation of core values, professional learning helps understand society, establish correct values, and promote personal and social progress. In December 2016, General Secretary Xi emphasized at the National Conference on Ideological and Political Work in Universities that "we must consistently prioritize moral education as the central link and integrate ideological and political work throughout the entire education process, achieving comprehensive education and all-round development, and strive to create a new landscape for the development of higher education in our country."^[2] Colleges and universities actively implement the spirit of the conference and fulfill the task of fostering virtue through ideological and political construction of courses. In May 2020, the Ministry of Education issued the "Guidelines for the Construction of Ideological and Political Education in Higher Education Curricula," stating, "Integrate ideological and political education throughout the talent cultivation system, and comprehensively advance the construction of ideological and political education in university curricula, maximizing the educational role of every course."^[3] The Guidelines require colleges and universities to ensure the comprehensiveness and consistency of ideological and political education.

Integrate ideological and political education into the course of Advanced Algebra, especially in the teaching of linear equations, to help students understand the social background and practical significance of mathematical knowledge, improve their mathematical thinking ability, and enhance their sense of social responsibility and values.

2 Current situation of ideological and political education in Advanced Algebra courses

In China's higher education, ideological and political education is the core of cultivating students' sense of social responsibility, moral concepts and comprehensive quality. However, its integration into different courses varies, with particularly obvious challenges in science and engineering courses. Ideological and political education aims to help students establish correct worldviews, outlooks on life and values, and cultivate their sense of social responsibility and moral consciousness. In science and engineering courses, ideological and political education needs to be combined with professional content to explore the relationship between science and technology and social development as well as their moral impacts, so as to achieve the dual cultivation of knowledge and values.

The problems faced by ideological and political education in the Advanced Algebra course include: the lack of ideological and political elements in the course content, insufficient awareness of teachers in integrating ideological and political concepts, single teaching methods, and a shortage of practical cases. To improve the current situation, it is necessary to strengthen the training of teachers in ideological and political education, innovate teaching methods, incorporate practical cases, formulate teaching guidelines, and enhance students' sense of social responsibility and values.

3 Path design for integrating ideological and political elements into the classroom teaching of "Linear Equations"

In the teaching of "Linear Equations", the "Nine Chapters on the Mathematical Art" and the spirit of craftsmanship are explained through the elimination method to cultivate students' quality of hard work and perseverance. This not only improves mathematical understanding but also enhances national pride, contributing to the development of the country.^[4]

3.1 Integrating ideological and political goals into the formulation of teaching objectives

The traditional teaching objectives of linear equations mainly focus on mastering several solution methods of linear equations and the theorems for determining the solvability of linear equations. In the strategy of integrating ideological and political education, the following two ideological and political objectives should be added:

(1) When learning linear equations, by telling the story of The Nine Chapters on the Mathematical Art and the ancient mathematician Liu Hui, students can feel the depth of mathematical history, stimulate their learning initiative, and enhance their national pride.

(2) By solving linear equations, students can realize the importance of accurate calculation and strict reasoning, thus experiencing the pursuit of excellence in the craftsmanship spirit.

3. 2 Integrating ideological and political elements into classroom introduction

A system of linear equations consists of unknowns, coefficients, and equality signs, with the elimination method being commonly used for solving. In teaching, mathematical history is introduced by combining The Nine Chapters on the Mathematical Art and Cramer's Rule, explaining the application and problem-solving skills of the elimination method, emphasizing practical applications, and encouraging students to summarize general methods for solving systems of equations.

Example 1 Solve the system of linear equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}x_1 + \frac{1}{3}x_2 + x_3 = 1, \\ x_1 + \frac{5}{3}x_2 + 3x_3 = 3, \\ 2x_1 + \frac{4}{3}x_2 + 5x_3 = 2. \end{cases}$$

Through a simple system of linear equations in three variables, help students review the application of the elimination method, recall and summarize the solution methods learned in middle school. Guide students to induce the solution methods of the system of linear equations in three variables through examples, draw inferences from one instance, explore the general solution strategies of linear equations, and feel the excellence in the craftsman spirit. At the same time, introduce the concept of elementary transformation of linear equations.

Definition 1 The following three transformations are called elementary transformations of a system of linear equations:

- (1) Swap the positions of two equations;
- (2) Multiply one equation by a non-zero number;
- (3) Multiply one equation by a number and add the result to another equation.

Example 2 Given a system of linear equations over the number field P :

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + a_1x_2 + a_1^2x_3 = a_1^3 \\ x_1 + a_2x_2 + a_2^2x_3 = a_2^3 \\ x_1 + a_3x_2 + a_3^2x_3 = a_3^3 \\ x_1 + a_4x_2 + a_4^2x_3 = a_4^3 \end{cases}$$

Where a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 are distinct from each other, prove that the system of equations has no solution.

In teaching, typical examples help students master problem-solving methods and achieve analogy. The introduction of new lessons presents The Nine Chapters on the Mathematical Art with Liu Hui's annotations to demonstrate ancient wisdom, enhancing national pride and inspiring students' striving spirit. Using Example 1 and Example 2 as carriers, the elimination method for linear equations and elementary row transformations are taught, focusing on the technique of quickly judging no solution when "0 ≠ 1" appears in the last row of the matrix. Through practicing similar problems, the idea of analogy is infiltrated, problem-solving errors are corrected, and accuracy and rigor are improved. The teaching process emphasizes cultivating students' craftsman spirit of excellence, integrating method mastery, cultural inheritance and quality shaping. It enables students to experience the dedicated and rigorous academic attitude in efficient problem-solving, achieving the unity of knowledge learning and value guidance.

3. 3 Integrating ideological and political elements into after-class assignments

Solve a system of linear equations by the elimination method

$$\begin{cases} 3x_1 + 4x_2 - 5x_3 + 7x_4 = 0 \\ 2x_1 - 3x_2 + 3x_3 - 2x_4 = 0 \\ 4x_1 + 11x_2 - 13x_3 + 16x_4 = 0 \\ 7x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3 + 3x_4 = 0 \end{cases}$$

By reading Liu Hui's The Nine Chapters on the Mathematical Art, students can immerse themselves in ancient mathematical contexts, appreciate the wisdom of the ancients, and select an elimination method problem for consolidation. This not only helps students understand ancient mathematical methods but also encourages them to cherish the modern learning environment and strive to improve their academic performance.

3. 4 Integrating ideological and political elements into classroom summaries

This lesson focuses on learning how to solve homogeneous linear equations using the elimination method and exploring the proof methods for their insolubility. By introducing Liu Hui's The Nine Chapters on the Mathematical Art, students not only feel the wisdom of ancient Chinese mathematics but also cultivate cultural confidence. During the process of students doing exercises, teachers promptly correct mistakes to improve the accuracy and rigor of students' problem-solving. This teaching method not only strengthens mathematical skills but also enhances students' sense of identity with traditional culture, helping students better understand the historical background and practical application of mathematical knowledge.

3. 5 Integrating ideological and political elements into teaching reflection

In course teaching, attention should be paid to students' learning status and overall class attendance. When integrating ideological and political elements, they should be vivid and specific, and sufficient time

for thinking and practice should be set aside when explaining new content. By introducing mathematical history such as "The Nine Chapters on the Mathematical Art", students can understand the wisdom of ancient Chinese mathematics and cultivate national pride and national identity. When learning the elimination method, emphasize the meticulousness of the craftsman spirit to inspire students to pursue perfection. This method not only improves the effect of mathematics learning, but also enhances students' cultural confidence and sense of responsibility, enabling students to achieve dual growth in academics and ideology.

4 Reflection and Improvement on the Integration of Ideological and Political Elements into Advanced Algebra Classes

Integrating ideological and political elements into advanced algebra classes aims to enhance mathematical ability while cultivating social responsibility and values. However, there are challenges in practical implementation that require reflection and improvement.

4.1 Reflection on the Integration of Ideological and Political Elements into Advanced Algebra Classes

There are three major problems in integrating ideological and political education into current Advanced Algebra courses: first, the content integration is not in-depth, only simply adding ideological and political elements, lacking systematicness and depth; second, insufficient teacher training, unclear methods and strategies for effective integration, resulting in lack of pertinence and effectiveness; third, single teaching method, relying on lectures and exercises, lacking innovation and interaction, failing to guide students to think about the connection between mathematics and society through cases or discussions, making it difficult for students to combine theory with practical problems.

4.2 Measures for Improving the Integration of Ideological and Political Elements into Advanced Algebra Classes

Integrating ideological and political elements into Advanced Algebra courses requires advancement from four aspects. Firstly, deepen content integration by systematically combining mathematical theories with social issues. For example, when explaining systems of linear equations, introduce cases such as resource allocation and environmental protection to help students understand the application of mathematics while recognizing social responsibility and value. Secondly, strengthen teacher training by conducting targeted programs to enhance teachers' ability to integrate ideological and political elements, including content on designing ideological and political teaching activities and guiding students in discussions on social and moral issues. Thirdly, innovate teaching methods by adopting diverse approaches such as situational teaching, case analysis, and interactive discussions. For instance, organizing group discussions on social responsibility in mathematical problems can increase students' interest in learning and their understanding of the connection between mathematics and social issues. Fourthly, establish an evaluation mechanism to assess the effectiveness of integrating ideological and political elements through student feedback, classroom observation, and

teaching effect analysis, and adjust teaching strategies accordingly. These four measures can effectively enhance the effect of ideological and political education, enabling students to enhance their sense of social responsibility and moral awareness while mastering mathematical knowledge, which is an important way to improve students' comprehensive quality.

4.3 Suggestions for Integrating Ideological and Political Elements into Advanced Algebra Classes

Integrating ideological and political elements into advanced algebra teaching can enhance students' comprehensive quality and sense of social responsibility^[5], providing a new perspective for teaching. The implementation suggestions include five aspects:

First, clarify the integration of teaching objectives and ideological and political goals, so that mathematics teaching not only imparts theories and problem-solving skills but also cultivates students' social responsibility and values. Second, design practical cases and projects, such as solving real-life and social problems through linear equations, to help students understand the social background of mathematical applications. Third, optimize classroom interaction and discussion; when explaining linear equations, organize discussions on their social applications, raise open-ended questions, encourage students to express views and analyze the social impact of different solutions to improve participation and ideological and political education effectiveness. Fourth, incorporate diverse teaching methods like case teaching, project-based learning, and flipped classrooms—case teaching helps understand the application of mathematical models through specific social issues, while project-based learning enables students to apply mathematics to solve real problems in team cooperation. Fifth, establish an effective evaluation and feedback mechanism; in addition to traditional mathematics assessments, set up ideological and political-related evaluation criteria, conduct comprehensive evaluations through project presentations and classroom discussions, and adjust teaching strategies based on feedback. Through these measures, the integration of mathematics teaching and ideological and political education can be achieved, cultivating high-quality talents with both solid mathematical foundations and social responsibility.

5 Conclusion

This paper explores the effective integration of ideological and political education into the Advanced Algebra course. Through case analysis and research on teaching strategies, it proposes strategies such as clarifying teaching objectives, designing relevant cases, optimizing classroom interaction, adopting diversified teaching methods, and establishing an evaluation and feedback mechanism. The study finds that integrating ideological and political education faces challenges such as the difficulty in integrating ideological and political elements with mathematical content, teachers' unfamiliarity with methods, and students' lack of interest. It is suggested to provide teacher training, design practical cases, and increase classroom interaction to ensure the effective integration of ideological and political elements and improve teaching quality.

Integrating ideological and political elements into the teaching of linear equations in the Advanced Algebra course helps to achieve comprehensive educational goals and enhance students' mathematical ability and sense of social responsibility. This research provides a useful reference for the practice of ideological and political education in higher education and lays a foundation for future teaching practice and research.

References

1. Xi Jinping. Young People Should Consciously Practice the Core Socialist Values: Speech at the Discussion with Teachers and Students at Peking University[N]. Guangming Daily, 2014-05-05(02).
2. Xi Jinping. Integrate ideological and political work throughout the entire educational process. [N]. Guangming Daily, 2016-12-09(01).
3. Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China. Notice on the Issuance of the 'Guidelines for the Construction of Ideological and Political Education in Higher Education Curricula. http://www.moe.gov.cn/srcsite/A08/s7056/202006/t20200603_462437.html.
4. Wang zhen. A Study on the Path of Integrating Ideological and Political Education into Higher Mathematics Teaching[J]. Forum on Industry and Technology,2023,22(20):78-79.
5. Chenhuihui. Implementation Strategies for Integrating Ideological and Political Elements into Mathematics Classroom Teaching in Higher Vocational Colleges[J]. Education and Teaching Forum,2023(51):165-168.